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БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/Zenodo.11301393>**ABSTRACT**

In this study, we investigated the safety of highly active antiretroviral therapy in HIV-infected patients. It is shown that as a result of the ineffectiveness and / or as a result of side effects of this therapy in 10.6% cases discontinued therapy performed or replacement regimens. One side effects of antiretroviral drugs - anemia occurs in 20.0% of HIV-infected patients and is often encountered when using regimens, containing azidotivudin (AZT). In 8.5% of cases, the procedure has been changed due to the development of diarrheal syndrome. In addition, as the side effects of antiretroviral drugs developed lipodystrophy, peripheral neuropathy, and an increase of alanineaminotransferase activity.

Key words: human immunodeficiency virus, highly active antiretroviral therapy, viral load, nucleotide and non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitor.

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**ОЦЕНКА БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ВЫСОКОАКТИВНОЙ АНТИРЕТРОВИРУСНОЙ
ТЕРАПИИ У БОЛЬНЫХ ВИЧ-ИНФЕКЦИЕЙ****АННОТАЦИЯ**

В этом исследовании изучалась безопасность высокоактивной антиретровирусной терапии у ВИЧ-инфицированных пациентов. В результате неэффективности данной терапии и/или побочных эффектов антиретровирусных препаратов 10,6% пациентов прекратили схему терапии или перешли на другие антиретровирусные препараты. Одним из основных осложнений применения антиретровирусных препаратов является анемия, которая наблюдалась в 20,0% случаев и наблюдалась преимущественно при применении

азидотимидинсберегающих схем. В 8,5% случаев причиной изменения схемы лечения стал диарейный синдром. Кроме того, в качестве побочных эффектов антиретровирусных препаратов также развиваются липодистрофия, периферическая нейропатия и повышение активности аланинаминотрансферазы.

Ключевые слова: вирус иммунодефицита человека, высокоактивная антиретровирусная терапия, вирусная нагрузка, нуклеотидный и ненуклеозидный ингибитор обратной транскриптазы.

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OIV INFEKTSIYASI BO'LGAN BEMORLARDA YUQORI FAOLLIKDAGI ANTIRETROVIRUS TERAPIYANI O'TKAZISH XAVFSIZLIGINI BAHOLASH

ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur ishda OIV infeksiyali bemorlarda yuqori faol antiretrovirus terapiyaning xavfsizligi o'rganildi. Mazkur terapiyaning samarasizligi va/yoki antiretrovirus dorilarning nojo'ya ta'sirlari natijasida 10,6% bemorlarda terapiya sxemasi to'xtatilgani yoki boshqa antiretrovirus dorilarga almashtirilish holati ko'rsatildi. Antiretrovirus dorilarning asosiy asoratlaridan biri kamqonlik bo'lib, u 20,0% hollarda kuzatildi va asosan azidotimidin saqlovchi sxemalar qo'llanilganda kuzatildi. 8,5% hollarda davolash sxemasining o'zgartirilishiga diareya sindromi sababchi bo'ldi. Bundan tashqari lipodistrofiya, periferik neyropatiya va alaninaminotransfera faolligining oshishi ham antiretrovirus dorilarning nojo'ya ta'siri sifatida rivojlandi.

Kalit so'zlar: inson immunitet tanqisligi virusi, yuqori faol antiretrovirus terapiya, virus yuklamasi, nukleotid va nukleozid bo'lmagan teskari transkriptaza inhibitori.

Kirish. Hozirgi vaqtda OIV infeksiyasini davolashning yagona usuli bu yuqori faol antiretrovirus terapiya (YuFART) [1, 2, 3]. YuFART davridan keyin bir qator opportunistik kasalliklarning tarqalishi keskin kamaydi va shu bilan OIV bilan kasallangan bemorlarning hayot sifati yaxshilandi [9, 12]. Mamlakatimizda YuFART 2006 yil aprel oyida boshlangan [4, 7]. Antiretrovirus preparatlar samaradorligi bilan bir qatorda nojo'ya ta'sirga ham ega [5, 8, 11]. OIV infeksiyasi bilan og'rikan bemorlarni o'ziga xos davolash uchun bugungi kunda 3 guruh antiretrovirus preparatlari amaliyotda keng qo'llaniladi: nukleozid teskari transkriptaza ingibitorlari (NTTI), nukleozid bo'lmagan teskari transkriptaza ingibitorlari (NBTTI) va proteaz ingibitorlari (PI). Inson immunitet tanqisligi virusi (OIV) fermentlarining ingibitorlari virus replikasiya qobiliyatini to'xtatadi va OIVning virusli yuklamasini (VYu) aniqlanmaydigan darajaga tushiradi [6, 10, 13, 14].

Tadqiqot ishning maqsadi: OIV infeksiyasi bo'lgan bemorlarda yuqori faol antiretrovirus terapiya (YuFART) o'tkazishning xavfsizligini o'rganish.

Tadqiqot obyekti va usullari. Mazkur ishimizda RIEMYuPKIATM Virusologiya ilmiy tadqiqot instituti klinikasi va Samarqand yuqumli kasalliklar klinik shifoxonasiga yotqizilgan OIV infeksiyasi bilan kasallangan 141 nafar bemorni statsionar davolanish uchun ko'rikdan o'tkazdik. Bemorlarning yoshi 18 yoshdan 69 yoshgacha. Tekshirilayotgan bemorlarning 57,5 foizini erkaklar (81 nafar) va 42,5 foizini ayollar (60 nafar)ni tashkil etdi. Barcha bemorlar turli xil YuFART qabul qiladilar.

Davolash davomida bemorlar epid anamnezi, kasallik tarixi, klinik tekshiruv, asosiy kasallikning og'irligini baholash olib borildi. Bemorlar YuFART buyurilganidan keyin 6 oy o'tgach, umumiy klinik, immunologik va virusologik ko'rsatkichlar bo'yicha o'rganildi. Terapiya samaradorligini monitoring qilish terapiya samaradorligini baholashning klinik va laboratoriya

mezonlariga muvofiq amalga oshirildi (OIV virus yuklamasi va CD4 limfotsitlari darajasini aniqlash).

Tadqiqotga kiritilgan bemorlarning aksariyati bir vaqtning o'zida dori-darmonlarni qabul qilishgan. Eng keng tarqalgan dori-darmonlarga quyidagilar kiradi: opportunistik infeksiyalarning oldini olish uchun terapiya, silga qarshi va qo'llab-quvvatlovchi yordam (simptomatik davolash).

Olingan natijalar muhokamasi. Tadqiqotdan olingan ma'lumotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, tekshirilgan bemorlarda samarasizligi yoki nojo'ya ta'sirlari tufayli 10,6% (15 bemor) hollarda YuFART rejimlari almashtirilgan yoki to'xtatilgan. YuFART xavfsizligi antiretrovirus terapiya boshlanganidan keyin 4 hafta, 12 hafta, 24 hafta va 48 haftalik monitoring tashriflari asosida klinik va laboratoriya parametrlarini yig'ish orqali baholandi.

ARV preparatlariga nisbatan erta nojo'ya reaksiyalar YuFARTni boshlashning dastlabki 12 haftasida kuzatilgan. Bularga azidotimidin (AZT) tufayli anemiya va efavirenz (EFV) tufayli kelib chiqqan neyrotoksik o'zgarishlar kiradi. Ritonavir (LPV/r) (8,50%) bilan kuchaytirilgan lopinavirni almashtirish og'ir diareya rivojlanishi bilan bog'liq edi.

YuFARTni kech almashtirishning eng keng tarqalgan sabablari lipodistrofiya va periferik polinevopatiya edi (1-jadval).

1-jadval

Ko'pincha davolash tartibini o'zgartirishga olib keladigan YuFARTning asosiy salbiy reaksiyalarining chastotasi (n = 15)

Klinik ko'rinishlar	Aniqlanish darajasi	
	abs.	%
Anemiya	3	20,0
Lipodistrofiya	2	13,3
Diareya	1	6,70
Periferik polinevropatiya	2	13,3
Depressiya	1	6,70
Toshma	1	6,70
Pankreatit	1	6,70
ALAT ko'tarilishi	2	13,3
Pansitopeniya	1	6,70
Trombotsitopeniya	1	6,70

Davolash tartibi almashtirilgan (yoki bekor qilingan) tekshirilgan bemorlar orasida 3 (20,0%) bemorda anemiya, 2 (13,3%) bemorda lipodistrofiya aniqlangan. Bir bemorda (6,70%) lipodistrofiya rivojlanishining sababi NTTI bo'lgan, bir bemorda davolash tartibining bir qismi sifatida azidotimidin qabul qilingan. Bir bemorda ritonavir bilan qo'shimcha ravishda lopinavir olganda diareya paydo bo'lishi davolash rejimini o'zgarishiga olib keldi.

Terapiya tartibini o'zgartirishga (bekor qilishga) olib keladigan YuFARTning nojo'ya ta'sirlari 1 rasmda ko'rsatilgan.

Rasm 1. Terapiya tartibini o'zgartirishga olib kelgan YuFARTga salbiy reaksiyalari (n=15)

Terapiya boshlanganidan boshlab dastlabki 3 oy ichida dorilarni almashtirish erta nojo'ya reaksiyalarning rivojlanishi, shu jumladan anemiya - azidotimidinga salbiy reaksiya rivojlanishi bilan bog'liq edi. Ritonavir bilan kuchaytirilgan lopinavirni almashtirish og'ir diareya rivojlanishi bilan bog'liq edi.

Keyinchalik YuFART davolash kursida dorilarni o'zgartirish sabablari ko'pincha lipodistrofiya, periferik polinevopatiya va pankreatit kabi ko'rinishlar bilan bog'liq edi.

YuFART xavfsizligi monitoringi natijalariga ko'ra, bemorlarning 60,0% YuFARTning bir yoki bir nechta komponentlari bilan bog'liq bir yoki bir nechta salbiy reaksiyalarni boshdan kechirgan. Aniqlangan noxush hodisalarning aksariyati jiddiy bo'lmagan, kutilgan yoki orqaga qaytadigan jarayon edi.

Bemorlarda kuzatilgan jiddiy salbiy reaksiyalar YuFARTning uchta komponenti: azidotimidin (zidovudin), nevirapin va efavirenz bilan bog'liq bo'lganlar sifatida baholandi.

Og'ir gematologik, gepatobiliar va psixiatrik o'zgarishlar oldindan mavjud bo'lgan xavf omillari bilan bog'liq edi: ya'ni anemiya yoki trombotsitopeniya, CD4 hujayralari soni (200 hujayra / mm³ dan kam), jigar kasalligi, surunkali komorbid kasalliklar, gepatotoksik dorilar yoki neyrotoksik dorilarni bir vaqtda qo'llash, anamnezida in'eksion giyohvand moddalarni iste'mol qilish, spirtli ichimliklarni suiiste'mol qilish, travmatik bosh jarohati va boshqalar.

Samaradorlik va xavfsizlikni kuzatmasdan turib uzoq muddatli davolash, davolash tartibi samaradorlikni sezilarli darajada pasaytiradi va salbiy reaksiyalar xavfini oshiradi. Ushbu tadqiqot ma'lumotlari shuni ko'rsatadiki, davolanish sifatiga ta'sir qiluvchi eng ko'p uchraydigan omillar: antiretrovirus terapiyaning salbiy ta'siri, anamnezida spirtli ichimliklarni suiiste'mol qilish va in'eksion giyohvand moddalarni iste'mol qilish, gepatotoksik dori-darmonlarni qo'llash va hamroh kasalliklarning mavjudligi hisoblanadi.

Xulosa:

1. Anemiya yuqori faol antiretrovirus terapiyaning asosiy salbiy ta'siridan biridir;
2. YuFARTning salbiy ta'siri, shuningdek, lipodistrofiya, periferik polinevopatiya va pankreatit kabi holatlarni ham o'z ichiga oladi;
3. Nojo'ya ta'sirlarning rivojlanishida ushbu hodisalarning rivojlanishi uchun birgalikda yoki oldindan mavjud bo'lgan xavf omillari kamroq ahamiyatga ega;
4. YuFART xavfsizligining doimiy monitoringi OIV bilan kasallangan bemorlarda davolanishni optimallashtirishga yordam beradi.

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9 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

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